

Table S2. Biochemical profile of the studied strains obtained using the Rapid ID 32A system

Biochemical test	Biochemical code	Substrate	Strain		
			ASD3451	ASD5720 ¹	ASD4241 ¹
Urease	URE	Urea	-	-	-
Arginine dihydrolase	ADH	L-arginine	-	-	-
α -galactosidase	α GAL	4-nitrophenyl- α D-galactopyranoside	+	+	+
β – galactosidase	β GAL	4-nitrophenyl- β D-galactopyranoside	+	+	+
β – galactosidase 6 phosphate	β GP	4-nitrophenyl- β D-galactopyranoside-6-phosphate-2CHA	-	-	-
α -glucosidase	α GLU	4-nitrophenyl- α D-glucopyranoside	+	+	-
β -glucosidase	β GLU	4-nitrophenyl- β D-glucopyranoside	-	-	-
α -arabinosidase	α ARA	4-nitrophenyl- α L-arabinofuranoside	+	+	+
β -glucuronidase	β GUR	4-nitrophenyl- β D-glucuronide	-	-	-
β -N-acetylglucosaminidase	β NAG	4-nitrophenyl-N-acetyl- β D-glucosaminide	-	-	-
Mannose fermentation	MNE	D-mannose	+	+	+
Raffinose fermentation	RAF	D-raffinose	+	+	-
Glutamate decarboxylase	GDC	Glutamic acid	-	-	-
α -fucosidase	α FUC	4-nitrophenyl- α L-fucopyranoside	+	+	+
Nitrate reductase	NIT	Potassium nitrate	-	-	-
Indole production	IND	L-tryptophan	-	-	-
Alkaline phosphatase	PAL	2-naphtyl-phosphate	-	-	-
Arginine arylamidase	ArgA	L-arginine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Proline arylamidase	ProA	L-proline- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Leucyl glycine arylamidase	LGA	L-leucyl-L-glycine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Phenylalanine arylamidase	PheA	L-phenylalanine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Leucine arylamidase	LeuA	L-leucine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Pyroglutamic acid arylamidase	PyrA	Pyroglutamic acid- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Tyrosine arylamidase	TyrA	L-tyrosine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Alanine arylamidase	AlaA	L-alanyl-L-alanine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Glycine arylamidase	GlyA	L-glycine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Histidine arylamidase	HysA	L-histidine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Glutamyl glutamic acid arylamidase	GGA	L-glutamyl-L-glutamic acid- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-
Serine arylamidase	SerA	L-serine- β -naphtylamide	-	-	-